

Assessing Student Sustainable Learning Engagement in Mobile Learning through Social Cognitive Theory and Social Learning Theory

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Abstract: The advent of mobile learning has revolutionized various facets of human life, including education. Mobile learning allows students to study anywhere and anytime which gives big opportunities to students access good education. However, sustaining students' learning engagement is challenging. In particular, this research identified the factors that can influence students' learning engagement in mobile learning from a social cognitive and social learning perspective. The factors including online learning environment, observational learning, and self-reinforcement and vicarious learning. This research also investigated the effectiveness of mobile learning tools in promoting sustainable learning engagement. This research collected questionnaires from 290 students who had experienced using a mobile learning platform and used Smart PLS 4.0 to test the hypothesis. The results indicate that the online learning environment and observational learning are the key variables that positively impact students' sustainable learning engagement. In summary, the result from this research suggests that students should have positive emotions to be willing to engage with the course then they will start to manage their behaviour to be suitable for an academic setting to start the process of learning and sustaining their engagement.

Keywords: Education, Sustainable Learning, Mobile Learning, Social Cognitive Theory, Social Learning Theory

1. Introduction

Mobile technology has significantly impacted the educational learning process including mobile learning (m-learning). It is the concept of allowing students to study at their convenience as the M-learning process gives more flexibility for students to balance their professional and personal lives. However, sustaining student engagement is challenging when students need to manage themselves through the learning process. This research aims to enhance understanding of sustainable student learning engagement through m-learning by applying Social Cognitive Theory (SCT) and Social Learning Theory (SLT).

Digital devices used for m-learning include smartphones and tablets to access the class and knowledge they want to acquire. It is flexible and convenient for students to search in the area they are interested in. However, maintaining long-term student engagement remains difficult. This study uses Social Cognitive Theory (SCT) and Social Learning Theory (SLT) developed by Albert Bandura. SCT focuses on observational learning and SLT focuses on reinforcement, behaviour formation, and social interaction in the learning process (Bandura, 1977; Bandura, 1986).

According to SCT, students' confidence in mobile devices and their belief in m-learning's effectiveness significantly influence engagement and outcomes (Wang et al., 2009). SLT underscores the importance of peer interactions and collaborative learning, which m-learning environments facilitate through features like discussion forums and group projects (Schunk & Zimmerman, 1997). Sustainable learning engagement is the ability to maintain interest, motivation, and active participation over time. Factors influencing this include content relevance, instructional design quality, and educator support (Reeve, 2012).

Although research shows many aspects of sustainable engagement contribution that can affect students' performance, this research investigates how SLT and SCT contribute technology to combine online study and human learning (Li et al., 2023). In particular, the conceptual model includes (1) an online learning environment (Video conferencing tools, social media, interactive tools, digital platform); (2) observational learning (modelling, imitation) from peers and instructors; (3) social reinforcement and vicarious learning (feedback, discussion). These variables were selected in this research because they can influence students' engagement. An online learning environment is about how convenient it is for students to use mobile learning to self-learn and study together in live sessions with friends. It is supposed to be easy to use, help students engage with course materials, be confident in searching for information, and allow them to improve their performance by doing quizzes, participating in discussion forums, and practicing exams (Moore et al., 2011). Observational learning is about adopting new behaviors by observing others' actions and thoughts. It is an effective way for students to learn from peers and instructors and also self-evaluate whether they can perform those behaviors appropriately. They also will evaluate if certain behaviors should be adopted or only observed for experiences (Li et al., 2023; Raedts et al., 2006). Social reinforcement and vicarious learning are how instructors appropriately communicate and provide feedback to students in order to improve students' performance and in-depth understanding of the course content. Appropriate feedback would help students learn what they need to improve and how they should improve by using the guidelines from instructors. It would help students to stay engaged with the courses. However, inappropriate feedback could disengage students and lead to dropout because the feedback may be good for students but inappropriate ways to communicate can lead to miscommunication (Akers & Jennings, 2015; Pleines, 2020; Wahab et al., 2013).

For students to successfully complete the mobile learning program, it is essential for students to stay engaged and have positive experiences to complement their future academic achievement and career (Brandisauskiene et al. (2021). It needs to consider behavioural and emotional as part of sustainable learning engagement as suitable behaviour for learning and positive emotion of students towards mobile learning is highly important (Cleveland-Innes & Campbell, 2012; Yang & Lamb, 2014).

M-learning can boost motivation and engagement through its interactive, and flexible nature. However, the long-term sustainability of this engagement is less understood. SCT's focus on self-efficacy and reciprocal determinism provides a framework for understanding sustained student engagement, while SLT's emphasis on social interactions has been effective in traditional and online learning, promoting engagement and retention.

The research objectives of this study can be broken down into two folds: to assess the effectiveness of mobile learning tools in promoting sustainable student engagement and to identify factors influencing sustained engagement in mobile learning from social-cognitive and social learning perspectives. Sustainable student engagement is a critical factor in achieving long-term educational success. It encompasses maintaining students' interest, motivation, and active participation in learning activities over an extended period (Fredricks, Blumenfeld, & Paris, 2004). Research indicates that engaged students are more likely to persevere through academic challenges, retain information, and achieve higher academic outcomes (Kuh, 2009).

2. Literature review

2.1 Sustainable learning engagement

According to Martin and Bolliger (2018) define student engagement as the student's psychological investment toward learning, understanding, and being an expert on the knowledge you have gained. Sustainable learning engagement includes behavioural and emotional engagement. Behavioural refers to the self-regulatory skills of students to develop habits to create an effective way of learning involving setting goals, completing assignments on time, and always participating in class (Yang & Lamb, 2014). Emotional engagement refers to how students actively manage their emotions to stay engaged in class and have positivity toward the course to overcome any difficulties through the course (Cleveland-Innes & Campbell, 2012). It means that learning engagement is the key solution for students either students will highly engage and have a strong motivation to learn through the learning program or face the issue of isolation and drop out from the courses. Student engagement in M-learning is very important because studying on an online platform may create fewer opportunities to be engaged with the institution. It means that if the content of the course makes students interested to enrol, so engagement is an important aspect to stimulate online learning these days. Further, engagement strategies can provide positive learner experiences including participating in a collaborative group assignment, discussing course materials among the students, and expanding connections to integrate case studies and self-reflections. Moreover, Brandisauskiene et al. (2021) explained that a higher level of student engagement connects with higher opportunities to achieve high academic achievement and future success. It is because students with high engagement normally get excellent grades as they prioritize their time to study and seek the best strategy for themselves to manage time to study. In particular, sustainable learning engagement in M-learning needs 3 elements: (1) online learning environment (video conferencing tools, social media, interactive tools, digital platform); (2) observational learning (modeling, imitation) from peers and instructors, and (3) social reinforcement and vicarious learning (feedback, discussion).

2.1.1 Online learning environment

Online learning environment is the design of learning objectives and design of the program such as self-paced which allow students to learn by themselves through available resources provided by the course program. However, the most common form of online learning environment is instructor-led as instructors coach and guide learners through the course under the course outline and instructions. All students expect to be at the same pace and participate in the same learning activities (Moore et al., 2011). Further, Martin and Bolliger (2018) describe that building activities in class are important to motivate students to engage with the course material and to focus on the class to prevent boredom and isolation such as chat sessions, group tasks, or peer assessment to allow students to give ideas, do the presentation, and give an opinion about the topic in class. The discussion board is also useful when students want to post their questions so an instructor and other students can discuss and find solutions together. There are many mobile applications including Google, Zoom, and Microsoft Teams create a better online learning environment for students to have their space to discuss, share ideas, and interact with other students.

2.1.2 Observational learning

Observational learning refers to the process of obtaining new behaviours and knowledge by imitating actions and expecting a similar outcome (Li et al., 2023). Observation is an effective way for students as it is how students observe their peers and instructors and store information in their memory for use later (Raedts et al., 2006). According to Bandura (1977) focuses on two representation systems imaginal and verbal. Imaginal representations of observed behaviour to peers or instructors under the condition of paying attention led to retention and reproduction of the knowledge. There are associations between names, places, actions, and characteristics when students hear the name of a certain person then it will trigger their imagination to think of that person's physical appearance or activities in a particular place and trigger their thoughts. The imaginal system allows students to recall actions and behaviours they have previously observed. A verbal representational system helps in long-term

retention. It may be faster and more efficient for cognitive processing as verbal code description of right-left-right may be easier to remember as it can convert the complex visual route into a more structured and easy-to-remember.

2.1.3 Social reinforcement and vicarious learning

Bandura's social learning theory is vicarious reinforcement and punishment as vicarious learning occurs in situations where students witness learning experiences by other students (Horsburgh & Ippolito, 2018; Pleines, 2020). Observing others is not only learning their behaviour but their mistakes and errors. Students also can learn from observing peers' reactions when they receive feedback from instructors. This is an efficient way to investigate how students will decide on either to reproduce or not reproduce the behaviour. It appears to be important to create opportunities for students to observe and learn from the outcome for them to self-reflect or discuss to adjust their behaviour (Horsburgh & Ippolito, 2018; Li et al., 2023). This is because students often learn through feedback provided by instructors to guide them to improve their performance. For this reason, formative and summative feedback is a way to give opportunities for students to self-reflect and adjust their work by learning from feedback to design what knowledge they have retained should reproduce in their current and future work projects (Apps et al., 2015). Reinforcement can be both positive reinforcement such as reward or positive feedback and negative reinforcement as punishment or negative feedback (Akers & Jennings, 2015). Negative reinforcement occurs when students get unfavourable experiences during the learning process such as punishment, warning, and negative feedback (Wahab et al., 2013). Although students who directly experience it may learn more vicarious students occasionally outperform students who interact directly. It is students' ability to take responsibility for their learning process and use vicarious learning as an instrument to achieve their academic goals (Pleines, 2020).

2.2 Hypotheses development

Considering the evidence in research about sustainable learning engagement in Mobile Learning, this research proposed that Online learning environment (video conferencing tools, social media, interactive tools, digital platform), observational learning (modelling, imitation) from peers and instructors, and social reinforcement and vicarious learning (feedback, discussion) could have a positive influence on firm performance.

2.2.1 Online learning environment and sustainable learning engagement

Student engagement is defined as the students' psychological investment in and effort toward learning, understanding, and mastering the knowledge (Martin & Bolliger, 2018). Sustainable learning engagement includes behavioural and emotional engagement. Behavioural refers to the self-regulatory skills of students to develop positive learning habits in class to achieve the academic goal (Yang & Lamb, 2014) while emotional engagement refers to how students actively manage their emotions to be suitable in each class environment to be able to stay engaged in class (Cleveland-Innes & Campbell, 2012). According to SCT mention about self-efficacy is a key component (Bandura, 1986) explains that students who have high self-efficacy can effectively manage their behaviour and inhibit distractions while engaging in class including participating in online discussions or completing assignments on time (Yang & Lamb, 2014). In addition, positive emotions such as enjoyment and interest in course content can reduce psychological barriers such as fear of judgment or anxiety as students feel more comfortable and willing to participate in class activities that involve interaction with other students to enhance their overall learning experiences (Imamyartha et al., 2021).

In order to influence students to engage with the learning course supposed to have a well-designed online environment to enhance the cognitive and self-efficacy process by motivating students to interact with peers and instructors through an M-learning digital platform including clear course

outlines and materials, pre-recorded lectures, discussion forum, or tutorial sessions. Moreover, the interactive tools are beneficial for peer-to-peer interactions and collaborative learning. Interactive learning resources such as quizzes, tutorial sessions, and repeatable exercises with many versions of different questions can engage with student-to-content interactions. Further, assignments and group projects encourage student-to-student interactions as students can use live chat and discussion boards to discuss the tasks together and receive peer feedback to adjust their work collaboratively. In addition, student-to-instructor interactions as students can receive feedback and suggestions from instructors through personal chat for individuals or discussion boards for all students (Martin & Bolliger, 2018; Moore et al., 2011). The well-designed mobile learning environment enhances cognitive processes including attention, retention, and reproduction by having a variety of engaging content to maintain students' attention and lead to retention the knowledge. Moreover, peer-to-peer, student-to-content, and student-to-instructor interactions can create deeper engagement with the course to enhance students' self-efficacy as they gain more confidence and lead to sustainable engagement through a mobile learning environment (Martin & Bolliger, 2018; Wang et al., 2009).

H1: The online learning environment positively influences sustainable learning engagement

2.2.2 Observational learning and cognitive and sustainable learning engagement

Learning through observation involves attention, retention, reproduction, and motivation as it affects the effectiveness of learning including passive observation and active feedback engagement. According to Bandura (1977), passive observation is how students primarily observe behaviours, skills, or actions of instructors and peers without directly interacting during the live sessions. It is aligned with the imaginal system as students will actively pay attention and form mental images or presentations that instructors have shown in class and observe how peers and instructors discuss certain issues. These situations they observed will keep and reproduce this behaviour later. Active feedback engagement involves interacting with peers and instructors by providing and receiving immediate feedback. This form of engagement is more complicated as it includes verbally encoding the behaviour and actions they have observed or experienced. Raedts et al. (2006) further explain that the benefit of the verbal system is allowing students to interact or ask questions which helps learners encode information and makes it easier to remember and reproduce the knowledge. This process can facilitate cognitive engagement by helping students understand what they have observed and reinforce their knowledge and skills. However, the students must have positive emotions and motivation to learn and be willing to reproduce the behaviour (Ariani, 2015; Raedts et al., 2006). Effortful control in the development of self-regulation allows students to manage their behaviour and cognition which affect successful engagement in learning (Yang & Lamb, 2014). According to Bandura (1986) explains that the most important element to start the learning process is attention so if students pay attention, then the learning process will begin and lead to retention and reproduction. In fact, behavioural engagement refers to the self-regulatory skill of students to manage their learning process to achieve learning outcomes so students who have high self-regulatory skills are likely to be able to observe and learn effectively from peers and instructors. Further, emotional engagement is always present in the learning process (Cleveland-Innes et al., 2013). Therefore, students who have strong intrinsic emotions can encounter challenges and can motivate themselves to focus and pay attention to observe peers and instructors' actions as they are willing to accept and adapt to what they have observed which increases the effectiveness and sustainable engagement of learning (Raedts et al., 2006).

H2: Observational learning positively influences sustainable learning engagement

2.2.3 Social reinforcement and vicarious learning and sustainable learning engagement

Social reinforcement involves feedback to help students improve their skills and behaviour. It includes direct feedback on assignments, rubric-based grading, and assessments. Rubrics offer clear performance standards to help students understand the criteria for successful assignments and assessments. Instructors have two ways to provide feedback including formative and summative to help students to adjust their behaviours and skill to develop learning outcomes (Alqurashi, 2016; Ariani,

2015; Imamyartha et al., 2021; Martin & Bolliger, 2018). The most important element is teaching presence to coach and train students in the direction of cognitive and social processes to achieve meaningful educational outcomes. It is where the feedback and guidance from instructors are critical to lead students toward productive learning experiences to support self-efficacy and cognitive engagement (Cleveland-Innes et al., 2013). Instructor feedback and guidance empower them to contribute knowledge and foster deeper engagement and collaborative learning (Imamyartha et al., 2021). Further, students prefer timely feedback that is detailed, personalised, and constructive. Students also expect to get video or audio feedback from the instructor to have a clearer understanding. Responsive and supportive instructors encourage students to get interested in the course as it develops the relationship with the students which makes them willing to connect to course materials and instructors (Martin & Bolliger, 2018). It has more ability to engage with students who have a perception of self-regulatory as they can regulate their actions and behaviour to receive feedback to adjust their work and overcome any challenges to meet the course requirement (Yang & Lamb, 2014). Further, emotional engagement is how students can stay motivated with positive emotions towards the course even though they have to face positive and negative feedback and accept to adjust and improve their performance and be able to sustain engagement through the course (Cleveland-Innes & Campbell, 2012).

H3: Social reinforcement and vicarious learning positively influence sustainable learning engagement

All hypotheses are summarized in the conceptual model, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual model: Shows the relationships between the independent variables and dependent variables

3. Research methodology

3.1 Sample and Data Collection

The sampling framework of this research are focusing on students in bachelor’s degree, master’s degree, and Ph.D. degree who have experienced m-learning from Thailand. This is because, during the pandemic covid-19, all students must study online and use digital devices such as tablets and smartphones to study online. It would be appropriate for them to provide feedback and thoughts on the survey as they have direct mobile learning experiences. The research will involve students from various educational institutions who use mobile learning tools. A sample size of approximately a minimum of 100 participants will be targeted. A self-administered questionnaire survey to collect the data using

Google Survey and email as the researcher has permission from certain educational institutions that allow researchers to email providing google form link to faculty members and they distributed to respondents to answer the questionnaires. The cover of the survey clearly explained the purpose of this study and guaranteed all information would be highly confidential, and the respondent's name remained anonymous the researcher also does not know who responded to the survey. However, the respondents can provide the email to the researchers if they want to get inform the result from this research. A total of 121 usable questionnaires were suitable for data analysis, which represented 93 percent response rate. Moreover, the ethical considerations were upheld throughout the research, with questionnaires and data collection conducted in accordance with the IRB-approved protocol. It is summarised in Table 1 and the questionnaire is presented in 3.2 measures.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of the respondents of this questionnaire

Variables		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Gender	male	26	21.5	21.5	21.5
	female	95	78.5	78.5	100.0
Age	18-25	76	62.8	62.8	62.8
	26-33	24	19.8	19.8	82.6
	34-41	13	10.7	10.7	93.4
	42-49	7	5.8	5.8	99.2
	50-57	1	.8	.8	100.0
Years of online learning experience	1-2	46	38.0	38.0	38.0
	3-4	30	24.8	24.8	62.8
	5-6	14	11.6	11.6	74.4
	7-8	3	2.5	2.5	76.9
	more than 8	28	23.1	23.1	100.0
Education	Bachelor's degree	85	70.2	70.2	70.2
	Master's degree	20	16.5	16.5	86.8
	Ph.D. degree	16	13.2	13.2	100.0

3.2 Measures

Online learning environment is measured by the scale developed by Martin and Bolliger (2018) and Chin-ChehYi et al. (2010). The scale consists of 10 questions. These items were rated on a five-point Likert scale that range from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

Observational learning is measured by the scale developed by Martin and Bolliger (2018). The scale consists of 10 questions. These items were rated on a five-point Likert scale that range from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

Social reinforcement and vicarious learning is measured by the scale developed by Bajaj et al. (2018) and Weaver (2006). The scale consists of 7 questions. These items were rated on a five-point Likert scale that range from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

Behavioural engagement is measured by the scale developed by Xiao and Jiang (2023) and Dmello et al. (2023). The scale consists of 10 questions. These items were rated on a five-point Likert scale that range from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

Emotional engagement is measured by the scale developed by Han and Wang (2021) and Nonis et al. (2020). The scale consists of 10 questions. These items were rated on a five-point Likert scale that range from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

3.3 Control Variables

This research also includes other control variables that may affect students' sustainable learning engagement including gender, age, years of online learning experience, education, and job. Age is measured by the age range. Education level is measured by the highest degree. Years of online learning experience is measured by the years the respondents have experience in online learning. There is also the question asked whether respondents ever use mobile phones or iPads as a tool to study. If the respondents have ever used then they can continue the survey, if not the survey will end with this question.

3.4 Statistical Analysis

The statistical method to analyse the data in this study is using SmartPLS 4.0 to test the measurement model to assess the reliability and validity of the constructs. The structural model was examined to test the hypothesized relationships to calculate the linear relationship between a set of independent variables and the dependent variable. SMARTPLS allows for models with both reflective and formative indicators, providing greater flexibility in model specification. Quantitative data is analysed through partial least square structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM). It is the data analysis tool that imperative to be utilized in business and social science researchers to analyse data efficiently. PLS-SEM use for two-phase analysis including measurement model specification and structural model assessment. Measurement model specification to further analysis the constructs with good indicator loading, convergent validity, composite reliability (CR), and discriminant validity. Structural model assessment weighs path coefficients and test their significance. PLS-SEM is also applied for data analysis in the empirical studies in the literature.

4. Research results

4.1 Reliability and validity

The reliability of the constructs was tested using Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability (CR). All items loading more than 0.50 and the results for reliability and validity and factor loadings are represented in Table 1. All the CRs and Cronbach's Alpha values were higher than 0.700. The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) all higher than 0.500 (Hair et al. 2010). The results in Table 1 show that all constructs' reliability and validity along with item loadings.

Table 2: Item loadings, reliability and validity results

Online learning environment		Alpha	CR	AVE
Ole1	0.764	0.94	0.94	0.638
Ole2	0.757			
Ole3	0.808			
Ole4	0.808			
Ole5	0.765			
Ole6	0.736			

Ole8	0.877
Ole9	0.877
Ole10	0.784

Observational learning

		Alpha	CR	AVE
Obl1	0.671	0.939	0.939	0.609
Obl10	0.872			
Obl2	0.622			
Obl3	0.718			
Obl4	0.778			
Obl5	0.865			
Obl6	0.835			
Obl7	0.858			
Obl8	0.697			
Obl9	0.838			

Social reinforcement and vicarious learning

		Alpha	CR	AVE
Sol1	0.939	0.956	0.956	0.755
Sol2	0.821			
Sol3	0.880			
Sol4	0.842			
Sol5	0.878			
Sol6	0.890			
Sol7	0.827			

Sustainable learning engagement

Behavioural engagement

		Alpha	CR	AVE
Bhv1	0.809	0.945	0.944	0.549
Bhv10	0.757			
Bhv2	0.578			
Bhv3	0.710			
Bhv4	0.813			
Bhv5	0.760			
Bhv6	0.818			
Bhv7	0.793			

Bhv8	0.795
Bhv9	0.743

Emotional engagement

Emo1	0.703
Emo2	0.600
Emo3	0.788
Emo4	0.654

Ole: Online learning environment, Obl: Observational learning, Sol: Social reinforcement and vicarious learning, Bhv: Behavioural engagement, Emo: Emotional engagement

4.2 Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)

Multicollinearity is detected by the variance inflation factor (VIF), which must be lower than 5. The results show that the highest VIF is the subject norm containing 4.817 which is less than the criteria. This provides sufficient evidence that multicollinearity is not considered an issue in this study.

Table 3: Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)

Control Variables	VIF
Gender	1
Age	1
Education	1
Years of online learning experience	1
Online learning environment	
Ole1	2.62
Ole2	1.954
Ole3	3.323
Ole4	3.544
Ole5	3.017
Ole6	3.605
Ole8	4.011
Ole9	3.381
Ole10	2.815
Observational learning	
Obl1	2.127
Obl2	2.082
Obl3	2.705
Obl4	3.089
Obl5	3.134
Obl6	3.689
Obl7	2.915
Obl8	3.277
Obl9	4.052
Obl10	3.483

Social reinforcement and vicarious learning	
Sol1	3.349
Sol2	3.991
Sol3	4.817
Sol4	3.544
Sol5	2.756
Sol6	4.239
Sol7	4.34
Behavioural engagement	
Bhv1	2.797
Bhv2	2.673
Bhv3	2.85
Bhv4	2.453
Bhv5	3.962
Bhv6	3.206
Bhv7	3.817
Bhv8	3.465
Bhv9	4.529
Bhv10	3.467
Emotional engagement	
Emo1	4.784
Emo2	4.028
Emo3	4.407
Emo4	4.776

Discriminant validity was assessed by comparison of the correlations among the latent variables and the square root of AVE, with the value below the conservative of 0.85.

The correlations among the variables in the model are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Correlations among variables

	Age	Ed	Gender	OBL	OLE	SUSTAINABLE	SOL	Year
Age								
Ed	0.608							
Gender	0.295	0.249						
OBL	0.06	0.06	0.09					
OLE	0.081	0.211	0.132	0.850				
SUSTAINABLE	0.07	0.143	0.11	0.793	0.8			
SOL	0.047	0.045	0.053	0.806	0.815	0.68		
Year	0.05	0.008	0.136	0.205	0.084	0.162	0.205	

OBL = Observational learning

OLE = Online learning environment

SOL = Social reinforcement and vicarious learning

SUSTAINABLE = Sustainable learning engagement

The results from the model estimation using SmartPLS 4.0 regression are summarized in Table 5. The results from hypotheses testing are shown as follows:

Table 5: Path coefficients - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Age -> SUSTAINABLE	-0.074	-0.075	0.084	0.886	0.376
Ed -> SUSTAINABLE	0.083	0.079	0.083	0.993	0.321
Gender SUSTAINABLE ->	0.107	0.09	0.164	0.655	0.513
OBL -> SUSTAINABLE	0.376	0.39	0.122	3.087	0.002
OLE -> SUSTAINABLE	0.451	0.437	0.158	2.859	0.004
SOL -> SUSTAINABLE	-0.001	0.012	0.164	0.005	0.996
Year -> SUSTAINABLE	-0.037	-0.034	0.065	0.573	0.566

Dependent variable: Sustainable learning engagement

Model Summary

Table 6: PLS predict LV summary - PLS – SEM

	Q ² predict	RMSE	MAE
SUSTAINABLE	0.542	0.701	0.481

Table 7: R-square overview

	Q ² predict	RMSE	MAE
SUSTAINABLE	0.542	0.701	0.481

The results from SmartPLS 4.0 path coefficient are summarised in the conceptual model for sustainable learning engagement including behavioural and emotional engagement as a dependent variable, as shown in Figure 2.

Notes: *p- value < .05, **p-value <.01
Standardized beta coefficients are reported.

Figure 2: Results from SmartPLS 4.0 path coefficient: Outlined the effect of the independent variables on Sustainable learning engagement including behavioural and emotional engagement

Hypothesis 1: There is a positive relationship between an online learning environment and sustainable learning engagement. A positive beta coefficient of the online learning environment is obtained ($\beta=.376$; $p<.01$). This means the online learning environment has a positive effect on students' sustainable learning engagement in mobile learning. This result is statistically significant.

Hypothesis 2: There is a positive relationship between observational learning and sustainable learning engagement. A positive beta coefficient of the online learning environment is obtained ($\beta=.451$; $p<.01$). This means observational learning has a positive effect on students' sustainable learning engagement in mobile learning. This result is statistically significant.

Hypothesis 3: There is a negative relationship between social reinforcement and vicarious learning and sustainable learning engagement. A negative beta coefficient of the online learning environment is obtained ($\beta=-.001$; $p>.05$). This means social reinforcement and vicarious learning have a negative effect on students' sustainable learning engagement in mobile learning. This result is not statistically significant.

Lastly, the r-square of the regression from sustainable learning engagement is 0.625. It means all the variables including gender, age, years of online learning experience, education, online learning environment, observational learning, social reinforcement, and vicarious learning can explain student sustainable learning engagement by 62.5 percent and can be explained by other factors by 37.5 percent that may not include in this study.

Table 8: Path coefficients - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Age -> BHV	-0.025	-0.025	0.084	0.3	0.765
Ed -> BHV	0.04	0.038	0.082	0.493	0.622
Gender -> BHV	0.217	0.205	0.16	1.357	0.175
OBL -> BHV	0.358	0.369	0.129	2.784	0.005
OLE -> BHV	0.399	0.387	0.158	2.519	0.012
SOL -> BHV	0.059	0.067	0.189	0.312	0.755
Year -> BHV	-0.072	-0.066	0.065	1.115	0.265

Dependent variable: Behavioural engagement

Model Summary

Table 9: PLS predict LV summary - PLS – SEM

	Q ² predict	RMSE	MAE
BHV	0.511	0.724	0.522

Table 10: R-square overview

	R-square	R-square adjusted
BHV	0.625	0.601

The results from SmartPLS 4.0 path coefficient are summarised in the conceptual model for behavioural engagement as a dependent variable, as shown in Figure 3.

Notes: *p-value < .05, **p-value < .01
Standardized beta coefficients are reported.

Figure 3: Results from SmartPLS 4.0 path coefficient: Behavioural engagement

Hypothesis 1: There is a positive relationship between the online learning environment and behavioural engagement. A positive beta coefficient of the online learning environment is obtained ($\beta=.399$; $p<.01$). This means the online learning environment has a positive effect on students' behavioural engagement in mobile learning. This result is statistically significant.

Hypothesis 2: there is a positive relationship between observational learning and behavioural engagement. A positive beta coefficient of observational learning is obtained ($\beta=.358$; $p<.05$). This means observational learning has a positive effect on students' behavioural engagement. This result is statistically significant.

Hypothesis 3: there is a negative relationship between social reinforcement and vicarious learning and behavioural engagement. A negative beta coefficient of social reinforcement and vicarious learning is obtained ($\beta= .059$; $p>.05$). This means social reinforcement and vicarious learning negatively affect behavioural engagement. This result is not statistically significant.

Lastly, the r-square of the regression from behavioural engagement is 0.601. It means all the variables including gender, age, years of online learning experience, education, online learning environment, observational learning, social reinforcement, and vicarious learning can explain student behavioural engagement by 60.1 percent and there is another 39.9 percent can explain by other factors.

Table 11: Path coefficients - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Age -> EMO	-0.19	-0.196	0.094	2.027	0.043
Ed -> EMO	0.138	0.134	0.101	1.357	0.175
Gender -> EMO	0.005	-0.011	0.221	0.025	0.98
OBL -> EMO	0.393	0.397	0.155	2.54	0.011
OLE -> EMO	0.409	0.409	0.168	2.438	0.015
SOL -> EMO	-0.167	-0.153	0.115	1.453	0.146
Year -> EMO	0.024	0.023	0.08	0.298	0.766

Dependent variable: emotional engagement

Model Summary

Table 12: PLS predict LV summary - PLS – SEM

	Q ² predict	RMSE	MAE
EMO	0.286	0.863	0.592

Table 13: R-square overview

	R-square	R-square adjusted
EMO	0.441	0.407

The results from SmartPLS 4.0 path coefficient are summarised in the conceptual model for emotional engagement as a dependent variable, as shown in Figure 4.

Notes: *p-value < .05, **p-value < .01
Standardized beta coefficients are reported.

Figure 4: Results from SmartPLS 4.0 path coefficient: Emotional engagement

Hypothesis 1: There is a positive relationship between online learning environment and emotional engagement. A positive beta coefficient of the online learning environment is obtained ($\beta=.409$; $p<.01$). This means the online learning environment has a positive effect on students' emotional engagement in mobile learning. This result is statistically significant.

Hypothesis 2: There is a positive relationship between observational learning and emotional engagement. A positive beta coefficient of observational learning is obtained ($\beta=.393$; $p<.05$). This means observational learning positively affects students' emotional engagement. This result is statistically significant.

Hypothesis 3: There is a negative relationship between social reinforcement vicarious learning and emotional engagement. A negative beta coefficient of social reinforcement and vicarious learning is obtained ($\beta= -.167$; $p>.05$). This means social reinforcement and vicarious learning negatively affect emotional engagement. This result is not statistically significant.

Lastly, the r-square of the regression from emotional engagement is 0.407. It means all the variables including gender, age, years of online learning experience, education, job, online learning environment, observational learning, social reinforcement, and vicarious learning can explain student emotional engagement by 40.7 percent and can be explained by other factors by 59.3 percent that may not include in this study.

5. Discussion and research implications

5.1 Discussion

The purpose of this research is to assess the effectiveness of mobile learning tools in promoting sustainable learning engagement among students and identify the factors that influence sustained engagement in mobile learning from a social-cognitive and social learning perspective. This research has three perspectives on the result from SmartPLS 4.0 path coefficient.

For sustainable learning engagement, the result from SmartPLS 4.0 has shown that online learning environments and observational learning have a significant relationship with students' sustainable learning engagement. However, social reinforcement and vicarious learning have a negative relationship with students' sustainable learning engagement.

The online learning environment is the most significant impact on students' sustainable learning engagement as the positive beta coefficient obtained ($\beta=.437$; $p<.01$). Sustainable engagement is

defined as students' psychological investment to understand and master the knowledge; indeed, it includes behavioural and emotional engagement to develop positive learning habit and adjust emotions to stay engaged in m-learning classes (Cleveland-Innes & Campbell, 2012; Martin & Bolliger, 2018; Yang & Lamb, 2014). Clearly, M-learning can be flexible and allow students to study at their own pace to better understand the course content and reproduce the knowledge (Pleines, 2020). This can bring joy, excitement, and a feeling interested in the course and willingness to stay engaged and contribute to the course materials or assignments (Imamyartha et al., 2021; Martin & Bolliger, 2018; Moore et al., 2011). In addition, positive emotions can reduce the negative feelings such as fear of judgment or anxiety and feel more comfortable to interact with peers and instructors to have better overall learning experiences (Imamyartha et al., 2021). Indeed, when students have positive emotions to invest in the effort to study then it increases students' self-efficacy to have more confidence to overcome any challenges even though they may be frustrated and anxious with the course self-efficacy can support them to be in progress instead of quitting the progress (Bandura, 1977; Raedts et al., 2006). Definitely, students who have positive emotions with strong self-efficacy will develop self-regulation to allow themselves to manage their behaviour to be suitable to the learning process which directly affects sustainable learning engagement to achieve their academic goal (Yang & Lamb, 2014).

Observational learning also significantly impacts students' sustainable learning engagement as the positive beta coefficient obtained ($\beta=.402$; $p<.01$). Observational learning refers to the process by which students perceive new behaviours by observing peers' and instructors' behaviour and consequences. Then they will design whether to imitate that certain behaviour by evaluating the consequences they have observed (Li et al., 2023; Raedts et al., 2006). The interaction among students can develop students' sustainable engagement by using formal and informal learning spaces such as online forums or online group meetings to encourage more communication in terms of sharing ideas and interests. It allows students to observe their peers and instructors and learn from different perspectives on the topic they discuss by observing how they think and their opinion towards it (Bandura, 1977; Cleveland-Innes et al., 2013; Imamyartha et al., 2021; Pleines, 2020). In addition, Cleveland-Innes et al. (2013) further describe how emotion corporate with behavioural engagement to create sustainable learning engagement when it comes to the observational process, SCT refers to self-cognitive explains that observation is not only about imitating the behaviour but self-evaluation, which means students will reflect their capability and confirm the knowledge by evaluate if they can achieve the goal successfully by observing their peers on how they achieve it (Bandura, 1977, Pleines, 2020). Clearly, students are not only modeling peers' and instructors' behaviour to stay engaged in class but they have evaluated what they have observed and create strong intrinsic and extrinsic emotions by having strong self-efficacy to be confident that they can face any challenges of academic tasks during learning process once and hold positive emotion to be able to achieve the goal (Bandura, 1977; Horsburgh & Ippolito, 2018; Raedts et al., 2006).

Social reinforcement and vicarious learning are negatively impacting students' sustainable learning engagement as the positive beta coefficient obtained ($\beta=-.346$; $p<.01$). This means that feedback is not the concept to help students and instructors have better relationships. Imamyartha et al. (2021) explained that feedback can create relationships between students and instructors to help students feel more comfortable to engage in class. Moreover, Cleveland-Innes et al. (2013) described that the most important element is coaching students in the direction of cognitive to achieve valuable educational outcomes where feedback and guidance from instructors are critical to students' learning experiences. However, students can face unfavourable experiences during the learning process considering it as negative reinforcement including punishment, warning, and negative feedback when instructors do not understand how to provide feedback to students appropriately (Akers & Jennings, 2015; Wahab et al., 2013). Students expect responsive and supportive instructors to provide feedback appropriately and constructively to encourage students to connect with course materials and instructors (Martin & Bolliger, 2018). Clearly, when students receive negative reinforcement, it can discourage them from the course and mistrust instructors. It directly affects students' emotional engagement as students do not have positive emotions to be involved and engage with the learning course which leads to not adjusting their behaviour to be disciplined and adapt to the learning structure setting. It is because students are discouraged with the course materials and mistrust the instructors. It is not beneficial to both instructors and students in the learning process. Further, there are many ways to deliver feedback, and appropriate ways to provide feedback to students are also important. If there is any feedback that is

supposed to be delivered face to face then instructors should ask students to meet privately to avoid misunderstanding as some messages may not be appropriate to send email as it may affect students' negative emotions and need face-to-face communication. However, online communication such as video calls or Zoom meetings also would help as both instructors and students will see each other's reactions and easily communicate (Alqurashi, 2016; Cleveland-Innes & Campbell, 2012; Yang & Lamb, 2014).

For behavioural engagement, the result has shown that online learning environment and observational learning have a significant relationship with students' sustainable learning engagement. However, social reinforcement and vicarious learning have a negative relationship with students' sustainable learning engagement.

The online learning environment is the most significant factor that positively impacts behavioural engagement as the positive beta coefficient of online learning environment is obtained ($\beta=.584$; $p<.01$). It is because the well-designed mobile learning environment enhances cognitive process including attention, retention, and reproduction (Martin & Bolliger, 2018; Wang et al., 2009). In order to engage students to pay attention and learn in class need activities to engage students with the course material and give ideas and opinions to allow them to reproduce the knowledge they have learned and observed (Martin & Bolliger, 2018). SCT mentions self-efficacy (Bandura, 1986) and explains that students who have high self-efficacy will have high self-confidence and believe in their capability to overcome any challenges. However, the result shows that a well-designed online learning environment would help students to have more confidence to do self-learning such as self-tests and practice exercises, research information to enhance their understanding by themselves, more understanding of the key ideas by reflecting on course experience including exams and assignments, and able to design their interest and use optional online resources to help them better understand the course material (Alqurashi, 2016; Moore et al., 2011; Yang & Lamb, 2014). It means an online learning environment could help contribute students to having strong self-efficacy effectively managing their behaviour and inhibiting distractions to achieve mobile-learning goals (Martin & Bolliger, 2018); Yang & Lamb, 2014).

Observational learning contains a positive beta coefficient ($\beta=.393$; $p<.01$). It shows a positive impact on behavioural engagement. Learning through observation is an effective way for students as it is how students observe their peers and instructors and store information in their memory for use later. Students observe to learn how to present and respond in class to share interests and learn new ideas. Further, students can improve their skills by watching how peers and instructors collaborate in class such as group work or group discussion to understand the dynamic of teamwork and collaboration (Raedts et al., 2006). Further, observational learning also refers to the process of obtaining new behaviours and knowledge by imitating others' actions and expecting a similar outcome. It allows students to see topics from different viewpoints by observing the way peers and instructors think and discuss in class and imitate the behaviour when they observe peers and instructors have positive consequences from their behaviour (Li et al., 2023).

Social reinforcement and vicarious learning have a negative impact on behavioural engagement. A negative beta coefficient is obtained ($\beta= -.360$; $p<.01$). Even though the hypothesis explained that vicarious learning involves learning from peers' experiences which help students to acquire knowledge without repeated trial and error and feedback from instructors and peers can encourage students to get interested in the course as they develop the relationship with peers, instructors, and course contents (Li et al., 2023; Martin & Bolliger, 2018). However, Akers and Jennings (2015) argued that reinforcement can be both positive and negative such as reward or positive feedback to motivate students or punishment, and negative feedback which can discourage students from engaging and developing relationships within the class and course material. Further, Apps et al. (2015); Wahab et al. (2013); Yang and Lamb (2014) explained that students often learn through feedback provided by the instructor to improve their performance but it can be unfavourable experiences during the learning process as punishment, warning, and negative feedback can lead to decreasing self-efficacy and change to the behaviour that may not contribute to the learning process which the consequences can be drop out, or fail achieve the M-learning goal.

For emotional engagement, the result from SmartPLS 4.0 has shown that observational learning and online learning environments have a significant relationship with students' sustainable learning

engagement. However, social reinforcement and vicarious learning have a negative relationship with students' sustainable learning engagement. It is the same direction as behavioural engagement.

Observational learning is the most significant factor that positively impacts emotional engagement as the positive beta coefficient of online learning environment is obtained ($\beta=.414$; $p<.01$). Emotional engagement refers to how students actively manage their emotions to stay engaged in class and overcome difficulties and negative emotions to accomplish the goal (Cleveland-Innes & Campbell, 2012). However, observation is how students observe behaviour, skill, or actions of peers and instructors. When it comes to observation students may observe both positive and negative actions and consequences of the actions and students will have to choose either to adapt or avoid the actions that they have observed (Bandura, 1977). The positive emotions include feeling good in class and feeling interested in mobile learning class. It makes them want to be involved in class activities to enhance their learning experiences. On the other hand, they may feel anxious and frustrated when they cannot perform well, cannot understand the course content, or face technical issues in mobile learning so they cannot keep up with the course (Imamyartha et al., 2021). However, SCT mentions self-efficacy as students who believe in their capability to overcome any difficulties by sustaining their self-reflection to observe, learn, and reproduce when they observe their peers on how they face the issues then it connects with student self-efficacy to confirm their ideas of believing in their capabilities and successfully achieve one's academic goal (Bandura, 1977; Cleveland-Innes et al., 2013; Pleines, 2020).

Online learning environments positively impact emotional engagement as the positive beta coefficient obtained ($\beta=.254$; $p<.01$). Online learning environments can give flexible schedules and design programs to be more self-paced which allows students to learn by themselves through available learning resources. It can bring positive emotions such as enjoyment and interest in the course content and digitalisation experience through M-learning (Imamyartha et al., 2021). However, it can bring fear, anxiety, and stress which can destroy students learning engagement in class but sometimes may help students. Altogether, emotion and learning cannot be separated as emotion plays a dynamic role in the learning process (Cleveland-Innes & Campbell, 2012). Self-efficacy from SCT (Bandura, 1977) explains that students can overcome any difficulties with the belief in their capabilities, self-efficacy is about confidence indeed students need to have strong intrinsic emotions to encounter challenges during the learning process. Therefore, students will experience less stress and anxiety and will adapt when difficulties occur. However, it is for students who have high self-efficacy (Bandura, 1977; Raedts et al., 2006).

Social reinforcement and vicarious learning negatively impact emotional engagement as the negative beta coefficient obtained ($\beta= -.328$; $p<.01$). Even though instructor feedback and guidance empower students to contribute knowledge and construct deeper engagement to the learning process. However, Alqurashi (2016) argues that feedback comes from the instructor in real-time which can either lead to higher self-efficacy by encouragement from the feedback, or low self-efficacy by discouragement feedback. Further, Ariani (2015) describes the concept of appropriate feedback is about communication between instructors and students supposed to be clear and accurate. The lack of communication skills from instructors with insufficient information will lead to distrust and decrease students' self-efficacy.

Overall, observational learning is the most important factor to sustain students' engagement in M-learning as students learn by observing instructors' and peers' behaviour and how they think in many different dimensions towards course contents. Further, students also can observe how others behave in learning to achieve their academic goals and able to apply that knowledge in assignments and projects. Importantly, students not only observe to adopt behaviours but self-evaluate whether they would be able to perform those behaviours. If they observe and realise that they cannot perform the same way then they may change their course and major to find the most suitable study course for them. On the other hand, students observe and evaluate whether they should adopt a certain behaviour as they can evaluate whether the certain behaviour is appropriate to adopt or supposed to avoid (Ariani, 2015; Raedts et al., 2006; Yang & Lamb, 2014).

6. Co-Author Contribution

The authors affirmed that there is no conflict of interest in this article. Author 1 carried out the data collection, prepared the literature review and writeup of the whole article. Author 2 wrote the research methodology and provided general comments.

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9. Appendix

Measurement of variables:

Online learning environment

Ole1: I feel I can remember and understand the course content after engaging with different formats (e.g., text, video, audio, interactive games).

Ole2: I feel that using optional online resources helps me better understand the material and improve my learning methods.

Ole3: I feel I can apply what I learn during live sessions (eg. class events, guest talks) to real-world or practical situations.

Ole4: Guided discussions help me to understand the mobile learning course content better.
Ole5: I feel confident in researching information on a topic and explaining it in my way.
Ole6: I think choosing materials I'm interested in helps me remember and understand the mobile learning course content better.
Ole7: Reflecting on my mobile learning course experiences, like using tools, exams, assignments, and projects, helps me remember and understand key ideas better.
Ole8: Working on real-life examples via a mobile learning platform (eg. case studies or projects) helps me use what I've learned in practical situations.
Ole9: I think self-tests and practice exercises via a mobile learning platform (like quizzes with different questions) help me see how much I remember and show me what I need to improve.
Ole10: The mobile learning system is easy to use and engages me in studying.

Observational learning

Obl1: I use a virtual lounge to meet informally with my peers to share interests and learn new ideas.
Obl2: I observe and learn about my peers' skills and interests by looking at their profiles on the learning system.
Obl3: I learned how to present myself or organize my responses by watching how my peers introduce themselves in icebreaker discussions.
Obl4: I learn how to lead or guide discussions by watching my peers as discussion moderators.
Obl5: I learned to see topics from different viewpoints by watching my peers choose the topic from a mobile learning course.
Obl6: I get new ideas for sharing my thoughts by watching how my peers use audio or video in their discussion posts.
Obl7: I improve my presentation skills by watching my peers' presentations, whether live or recorded.
Obl8: I learned new ways to work in groups by watching how my peers collaborate with online tools.
Obl9: improve my work by watching how my peers give and respond to feedback in peer reviews.
Obl10: I learned to assess team dynamics by watching how my peers evaluate the contributions of team members in projects.

Social reinforcement and vicarious learning

Sol1: The instructor's feedback during discussions or on early drafts of my assignments helps me understand better.
Sol2: The instructor's feedback during discussions or on early drafts of my assignments gives me more time to improve before the deadline.
Sol3: Getting feedback early helps me understand better and find ways to improve my work before the deadline.
Sol4: The instructor's feedback during discussions helps me reflect, rethink, and deepen my understanding.
Sol5: I find it helpful when the instructor gives feedback in different ways, such as text, audio, or video, to help me understand it better.
Sol6: Feedback during the assignment and learning process gives me multiple chances to improve my work before submitting the final version.
Sol7: The instructor's clear feedback (like final grades, rubrics, and comments) helps me reflect and clearly understand my overall performance and how to improve next time.

Behavioural engagement

Bhv1: I set aside a regular time each week to work on the mobile learning platform.
Bhv2: I took notes while studying on a mobile learning platform.
Bhv3: I revisited my notes when preparing for mobile learning related assessment tasks.
Bhv4: I often searched for further information when encountering something in mobile learning that puzzled me.

Bhv5: When I had trouble understanding a concept or an example in mobile learning, I went over it again until I understood it.

Bhv6: If I watched a video lecture that I did not understand at first, I would watch it again to make sure I understand the content.

Bhv7: I was inspired to expand my knowledge through a mobile learning platform.

Bhv8: I often responded to other learners' questions.

Bhv9: I contributed regularly to course discussions.

Bhv10: I shared learning materials (e.g., notes, multimedia, links) with other classmates in the mobile learning platform.

Emotional engagement

Emo1: When I am in a mobile learning class, I feel good.

Emo2: When we work on something in mobile learning class, I feel interested.

Emo3: I enjoy learning new things in mobile learning classes.

Emo4: When we work on something in mobile learning class, I get involved.

Emo5: I often feel stressed when trying to keep up with the course workload.

Emo6: I feel anxious about whether I can perform well in mobile learning courses.

Emo7: I feel frustrated when I don't understand in mobile learning class, even though I've tried my best to understand it.

Emo8: I get frustrated when technical issues in mobile learning as it is difficult to keep up with the course.